

Politicisation of Corruption: A Driving Force behind Conflicts and Development Crises in Nigeria's Niger Delta

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Abstract

The development crises in Nigeria's Niger Delta Region have been attributed to myriad factors. These include marginalisation and frustration among local communities, resource control (oil revenue) and environmental degradations resulting from oil exploration and exploitation. However, these explanations are not necessary compatible and no doubt improve one's understanding of the crises from a variety of standpoints. This paper made the case that in order to comprehend the issues in the region holistically and find a solution, it is necessary to place it within the context of corruption, which has an impact on all regional development initiatives and policies. To support this position, this study gathered and analysed data from the Nigerian state (federal government) allocations to Niger Delta States for a period of eight years and compared to other geopolitical zones in Nigeria. The paper concluded that resource control and topography of the area are not the only problems affecting the region but also the major issue is politicisation of corruption in the region.

Keyword: Politicisation of corruption, Development crisis, Nigeria, Niger Delta Region

Introduction

The tremendous natural wealth of Nigeria's Niger Delta contrasts with the region's obvious underdevelopment. Crude oil is, in fact, more of a curse than a blessing in the Niger Delta. The reality that oil riches have tended to be bled away by some public officials, distorting the region's development and leaving the people poor and suffering, informs such a perspective. Stakeholders in the region used corruption as a "political weapon" to give an impression to people of the region that nothing is being done by federal government and oil companies operating in the area to address the region's development crises. At present, corruption is a tool by some stakeholders to determine resources, which does not correspond to development in the region, largely because it is a powerful weapon in the hands of political elites. The region is struggling to fully realise its development potential for decades due to massive fiscal leakages caused by widespread corruption at all levels. Nigeria, for example, is ranked 149th out of 176 countries in the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) for the year 2020 and 2021 respectively (CPI, 2021). It is obvious that states in the region have highest percentage of corruption in the national ranking. Indeed, the region's pervasive corruption has caused successive governments to squander development chances that could have lifted vast segments of the population out of the grip of harsh and vicious poverty. Corruption continues to jeopardize the region's development potential, as monies intended for development are frequently embezzled. As a consequence, a culture of corruption comes to the top of the political agenda in the area when the public treasury is looted with impunity.

Therefore, one of the study's fundamental questions is whether the region's development challenges are the result of a general Nigerian state failure or regional politicisation of corruption. This is largely because of existing literature on the region's deteriorating patterns of underdevelopment is attributed to topography, marginalisation and resource control as well as defective structure of federalism in Nigeria which often continues to occupy the thoughts of many scholars (Ogundiya, 2011a). While other studies indicated that the region is characterised by physical difficulties and challenges, including extreme poverty (Ross, 2003), political and economic instability (Aunty, 2001), environmental degradation and negligence of oil multinational operating in the region (Ikelegbe, 2005), widespread corruption in Nigeria generally (Gylfason, 2001), problems of fiscal federalism (Ikporukpo, 2000), Youth conflicts and militancy (Obi, 2010), slow economic growth and the threat of undeclared war as a result of ongoing conflicts among others (Yates, 1999). Indeed, the failure to apprehend the region's situation is one of the reasons why the

wrong remedies/policies have been implemented, making the crises worse than ever. As a consequence, this study appraised the existing literature on development crises in the region and also contributes to knowledge by arguing that it is critical to assess the region's development tragedy from the perspective of how political leaders' corruption and mismanagement have negatively impacted on the development of Niger Delta region. In order to do this, the paper compared and examined the distribution of revenue throughout the thirty-six states of the federation during an eight-year period, from 2010 to 2018, and arrived at the conclusion that, if resources are managed judiciously, regional development will have surpassed that of other political zones of the country.

An overview of the Niger Delta's historical context

The Niger Delta region is located in the Southern part of Nigeria. The region is about 70,000 square kilometer of geographical area that is diversified and multi-culturally diverse (Saro-Wiwa, 1996 & Tamuno, 1999; Titus, 2017). Bayelsa, Rivers, Delta, Edo, Akwaibom, Ondo, Cross-River, Abia, and Imo are the nine states that make up the area politically. To scholars like Obi & Rustad (2014) and Oluwaniyi (2011) the region has three states namely, Rivers, Bayelsa and Delta states in terms of oil quantity and petro-violence and insurgency.

Over 800 oil-producing communities can be found in the Niger Delta, which is home to an estimated 30 million people (Kemedi, 2003; National Population Commission- NPC, 2006 & 2016) with over 40 different ethnic groups and about 250 dialects including those of Ijaw, Itsekiri, Urhobo, Bini, Ukwuani, Ikwere, Kalabari, Andoni, Okirika, Ibibio, Efik, Andoni, Anang, Ogoni, Igbo, Yoruba and Ogba among several others (Onosode, 2003; Titus, 2017; Titus & Abubakar, 2020).

The region is one of the largest wetlands in the world comparable to the Mekong, the Amazon and Ganges (Mahler, 2010; Tonwe & Aghedo, 2013). It is home of the largest oil-producing communities in Nigeria (Titus, 2017). Nigeria's economic backbone is the Niger Delta. The region produces all of the offshore and onshore oil that provides more than 80% of the nation's annual income (Obi, 2014; Ibekwe, 2014). Additionally, it is known that this area is notorious for violent clashes between the different competing interest groups, including resource control agitators, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN), criminal gangs, and multinational oil corporations (MNOCs) (Ibekwe, 2014; Ejibunu, 2007; Titus, 2017).

Conceptual clarifications

Corruption

In political science literature, as in many other academic disciplines, the term “corruption” is very broad in scope. In this regard, it goes beyond many legal definitions of corruption, which has a tendency to focus primarily upon bribery. Corruption in its broadest sense refers to gaining an undue advantage (Rose & Heywood, 2013). The abuse of entrusted power for private benefit, for example, is an often quoted definition of corruption (TI, 2018). Because of its scope, any definition of corruption should include not only bribery, but also improper influence, nepotism, and inappropriate agreements, among other things.

However, it is possible to claim that numerous attempts have been made to establish more operational, less ambiguous, and culturally relative definitions of corruption. This paper defines corruption any act that is not only contrary to legal and moral norms, but also undermines the capacity of the Niger Delta region to experience development and secure the welfare of all its citizens. It refers to as an act that undermines the public good for personal or individual gain. The forms of corruption in this study are; embezzlement, bribery, looting, theft and money laundering, distortion of government expenditure, political patronage, and cronyism. Thus, it is difficult to define corruption, and hence it is vital to work within a definitional framework. The above

definition encompasses the majority of the concept's current meanings and applications in both contemporary social sciences and modern politics.

Development

The concept of development, on the other hand, has numerous definitions associated with it; it is a complex concept. Theorists of development such like Todaro (Economist) and Talcott Parson (Sociologist) do not actually provide a comprehensive definition of development. For instance, the term "development" does not necessarily refer to a specific standpoint on social, political, or economic growth. Instead, it serves as a collective word for a multitude of methods for changing unfavourable socioeconomic and environmental circumstances (Pearson, 2000). Instead of being solely an economic phenomenon, development is a multifaceted process that necessitates the reorganisation and change in direction of the entire economic, social and political system. It entails a process of increasing the quality of all human lives by focusing on three key aspects: human development, gender development, and a human poverty development index that incorporates all development indicators, including economic, social, and demographic figures (Todaro, 2003). For analytical purposes, development is conceived as the improvement of people's living standards which includes improved education, incomes, skills development, and adequate access to information, good infrastructural facilities, decent housing for the populace, and employment opportunities in the modern sector. It also refers to qualitative and quantitative changes in the living standards of the region's inhabitants, such as improved road networks, skill development, suitable housing, security, and other infrastructure improvements. It also entails strengthening people's ability to affect their own future for the better at the grassroots level.

Methodology

A qualitative approach based on documentary sources was used for the collection and analysis of data. Documentary sources in this study were generated from archives, textbooks, journals, magazines, reports, facts and figures from the official website of the ministry of Niger Delta Affairs, Senate Adhoc Committee Reports, Federal Ministry of Finance Bulletins, government publications, news release by militant groups, reports from international organisations, and other publications. These sources were very helpful in this study because the archival materials were analysed. The source offered fundamental advantage because it was a potential source of good quality data, largely within reach and cost effective, which were the main reasons of this method adopted in this study. The utility of documentary research enabled the researcher to have a deeper understanding of a phenomenon as well as theoretical and empirical knowledge that guide the process of data analysis and interpretation.

Theoretical underpinning - greed and grievance theory

The argument over greed and grievances brought to light how conflict economies create and sustain violence. The initial finding was that conflicts may be explained by an oversupply of lootable resources rather than disputes about a lack of resources (civil wars) (Collier & Hoeffler, 2004). While this emphasises the "greed" of conflict entrepreneurs as a primary cause of violent conflict, others place more emphasis on "grievances" as the inspiration behind conflict (Gurr, 1993). The theory of greed states that a form of self-enrichment (economic incentives) is the underlying motivation for militia to enter into violent conflicts in a given polity (Van-Itallie, 2014). According to Collier and Hoeffler (2004) civil wars (conflict) break out because of the greedy behaviour of a militant organisation that is willing to fight the government to satisfy their greed. In other words, the model as used in this study, posited that violent conflicts occur on greed (looting and personal enrichment by leaders) not because of grievance (political marginalisation, exclusion and neglects).

In this theory, greed means the economic opportunities to rebel or to start a revolution, and is contrary to the socio-political reasons that are represented by the grievance theory. Murshed (2009) stressed that “greed is about opportunities faced by the rebel group”. The greed theory could be disaggregated into four different opportunity components namely; financing, recruitment of manpower, geography and history of violence (Collier & Hoeffler, 2004). Based on Collier and Hoeffler's (2004) assumptions, this paper maintained the Greed thesis, which argued that those who redistribute oil revenue accruals use public funds for their own personal gain (greed) instead of serving the interests of the public for which they were elected or appointed.

This study defines greed as a violent power struggle between elites over the control of natural resource rents. The violent fight for control of natural resource rents is not necessarily for the good of the people those competitors pretend to speak for, but rather for their own personal gain. Fish, crude oil, lumber, gold, and diamonds are a few examples of the natural resources that provide these rents, for which the elites compete. The elites' self-interests are frequently served more by controlling the rents from natural resources than the general welfare of the population. In his work *Greed Versus Grievances Theories in Economics of Conflicts*, Pandit (2012) backed this up. The author made the argument that the elites' self-interest (greed) to control their own nation's natural resources drives them to take part in violent uprisings in resource-rich nations. They could include representatives of the government, insurgent group leaders, local community leaders, business executives, and other social elites.

In the case of militias in the region, control of resources is more likely to motivate them than genuine political problems with governmental authority, ethnic differences, or other factors frequently linked to violent conflict. Some of the key factors that may be causing violent disputes in the area are economic hardship, environmental degradation, and cultural incompatibility. The greed and grievance theory of the Niger Delta is illustrated in the graphic below.

The Researcher, 2023

It is obvious that the severe ecological effects of oil exploitation on the local population's economic base are the main reason for oil-related conflicts in the Niger Delta. According to this theory, the Niger Delta's ecology has suffered from decades of oil exploitation to the point where pre-existing production patterns in the surrounding communities have undergone a permanent

change. The local community violently reacted after the Nigerian government and foreign oil companies failed to address pertinent issues.

However, the aforementioned idea is crucial for comprehending how economic interests contribute to the persistence of violence in the corruption nexus. The conflict economy, for instance, is characterised by elements like clientelism, nepotism, bribery, and fraud (Cramer, 2006). Contribute to both profit-making and the complaints of individuals who are affected by corrupt processes (of those who benefit). Thus, a crucial issue to address throughout conflict-to-conflict settlement transitions is the role of corrupt practices and institutions in the region in generating complaints and opportunities for "greedy" conflict entrepreneurs.

Ikelegbe (2010) claimed that resentment might swiftly turn into greed in his analysis of the political economy of resource conflicts. Although grievances may drive oil-related conflicts, the desire to exploit the situation for private gain (corruption) may drive the conflict's continuation, particularly when the participants (state and non-state actors) profit directly or indirectly from the conflict. As a result, corruption has a close relationship to the region's nuanced conflict history. Due to the greed of a small group of state elites, the majority of the population was denied the advantages to which they are constitutionally entitled as citizens (i.e., the desire and opportunity to get wealthy through control of natural resource rents). The region's elites employ a number of strategies, such as bribery, political favouritism, political patronage, and theft of public monies, to maintain control over natural resource rents. For instance, former governors and their cronies in the region built luxurious residences in Nigeria's major cities using government funds. The elites' private profits are satisfied as imagined entitlements, but the majority of people are denied basic welfare that the state owes them as social obligation, supporting corruption that causes and/or maintains complaints (conflicts) in the state.

The greed and grievance thesis, thus, has the potential to explain the link between conflict, corruption, and development crises, but a cursory examination reveals that the grievance aspect of the analysis does not always lead to violent conflict. This is because greedy politicians have a monopoly on violence, and they could choose not to start a violent fight since they profit from the resources' proceeds, like in the case of the region under investigation.

Corruption and development crises in the Niger Delta region

The region remained the least developed section of the country in both physical and socioeconomic dimensions since the discovery of crude oil. This is largely attributed to misappropriation of funds meant for infrastructural and human capital development. At both the state and local government levels, the region is plagued by poor administration, poor leadership, and corruption among government personnel. It was stated that when politicians in the region had used their monthly funding wisely to create jobs and improve the region's infrastructure, the situation would not have become as dire as it is now. Corruption and inadequate governance have slowed the region's progress throughout the years. Some stakeholders have been accused of being behind the failure of past intervention programmes in the region that were supposed to change the region into a better society. Ineffectiveness, lack of concentration, insufficient and erratic funding corruption and bad governance lead to bureaucratic waste, excessive political meddling, and lack of transparency (Ogundiya, 2011b; Titus, 2017).

Additionally, the oil multinational had alienated the inhabitants in the region by encouraging extensive corruption and environmental devastation. Interethnic conflict and betrayal have occurred from oil firms' payments for lands that were taken and ruined. Criminal acts like as piracy, hostage-taking, kidnapping, and bunkering have now transferred the militants' real battle for socio-economic justice of the impacted areas to more selfish demands. The leaders of the region are taking advantage of the inhabitants. Instead of legitimately fighting for the people, the region's kings, chiefs, and politicians are just interested in their own financial gain. They were collecting the limited resources that the government and oil companies released for the region's development

(Ikelegbe, 2005). Corruption contributed to the Niger Delta crisis; some government representatives and officials are involved in corrupt activities, which clearly affect the socio-economic and political well-being of the populace. In fact, corruption is the primary factor contributing to the Niger Delta's underdevelopment, not merely one of its causes (Titus, 2017).

Budgetary expenditures are systematically organised to enrich individuals who wield state power in nations where corruption is widespread, particularly in mineral-rich states, according to the greed framework of analysis used in this study. Oil, as Ross (2004), points out, stymies democracy and degrades politics by causing governing systems to fail. Rents are generated by oil, which fuels corruption. Corruption is rampant among both militias and political elites. Oil, corruption, and government failure all play a role in tying the élites and insurgents together in a vicious loop. One popular method is to focus large amounts of public money on exorbitant white elephant projects that have little or no relevance to the public good but provide officials with a limitless potential to enrich themselves through kickbacks paid with budget dollars (Ibada & Okolo, 2005).

This tendency, on the other hand, aligns with the World Bank's definition of corruption, which includes the illicit diversion of public funds, as well as government officials' patronage or nepotism, and the theft of public assets (World Bank, 1997). The World Bank report backs up the widely held belief - corruption is defined as the abuse of public office for private gain. This includes instances in which regional public officials take, solicit, or extort bribes, as well as instances in which private actors give bribes to evade or subvert governmental policies for competitive advantage and profit (Ewharieme & Cocodia, 2011). Indeed, the insecurity in the Niger Delta region is the product of persistent economic and financial greed, which has resulted in some of the region's greatest levels of poverty (Titus & Abubakar, 2020). Violence has been proven to be a strategy of obtaining economic empowerment in the face of poverty and misery (Collier & Hoeffler, 2004). It is worth noting that it pays for those involved in economic greed to keep the region disorderly and insecure so that they can continue their illegal deeds within the region (Titus & Abubakar, 2020). The elites' economic avarice in the Niger delta is closely linked to poverty and inequality distribution, which fuel violent conflict in the region.

The region's elites have capitalised on the misuse of public power for private benefit, even where there are checks and balances, in furthering the greed argument in this study. Day paddle contracts, receiving mobilisation payments and not executing the contracts, poor performance, arranging for kickbacks, hiring relatives, or delivering gifts are all methods of gaining government contracts and money in the region. This was captured when Titus & Abubakar (2020) argued that:

The enormous revenue assigned to states and local governments in the region from the Federation Account, Derivation Fund and Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) fund did not have desired impact largely because the development agenda of these authorities have not been people centred and participatory. Corruption, mismanagement, rampant human right abuses, inadequate access to justice and human security, and the vulnerabilities of most of the population heighten frustration and alienation from all levels of government and other structure.

This implies that during the years of oil exploration and production, corruption and mismanagement of the region's money have slowed growth and exacerbated poverty in the region. State governors in the region have emerged as a powerful political force in the region, with 13% derivation funds worth billions of dollars. This resource's management is not transparent or accountable (Titus & Abubakar, 2020). In spite of the Niger Delta's bad track record, the wealthy, especially the governors, continue to enjoy luxurious lives thanks to their ill-gotten wealth.

Furthermore, political offices in the region are treated as investments rather than public services as in the case of elections in Bayelsa and Rivers states, respectively. Political patronage continues unabated; local government council officials are elected with the help of some powerful members of their political parties. This political patronage (godfather) frequently expects contracts or development projects to be completed in his hometown as the case of NDDC officials. Because

of the insincerity of political leaders in the region, all of the government's developmental programmes aimed at ensuring peace and development have failed to achieve their goals. Politicians and staff from the NDDC frequently divert funds intended for regional development. For example, Timi Alaibe, the then-NDDC Chairman, was accused of granting contracts worth ₦23 billion to his relatives, which were never completed due to NDDC corruption (Babalola, 2014).

There are other cases of economic greed and corruption in the region. Former governors of the states of Bayelsa, Delta, Akwa Ibom, and Rivers, including the late Diepreye Alamieyeseigha, James Ibori, Victor Atah, Timipre Sylva, and Peter Odili, were implicated in notable corruption cases in the area, notably from 1999. The region became extremely impoverished as a result of the enormous corruption that took place in the aforementioned States. For instance, it was discovered that the late Alamieyeseigha, who was arrested in London in September 2005 and later impeached for engaging in corrupt behaviour, allegedly squandered \$1 million in his London home, in addition to the \$420,000 and \$470,000 discovered in his various accounts, as well as assets worth \$10 million (Babalola, 2014).

In addition, Nigeria's Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) accused the ex-governor of sanctioning many dubious contracts and payments totalling ₦1.7 billion in favour of eight unreal firms, as well as other contracts worth ₦667,258 million issued to false organisations (Titus, 2017). The former governor was found guilty of money laundering and other corrupt activities and given a two-year prison sentence by a Lagos High Court in July 2007. However, he was released two days later because he had already served two years in jail since his arrest (Ibekwe, 2014).

Similar to this, the Nigerian Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) reported in late 2006 that it had conducted an investigation into the finances of the Rivers state and found that over N100 billion had been siphoned into private bank accounts while Peter Odili was governor. The report included accusations of fraud, misappropriation of public funds, currency manipulation errors, money laundering, and other offenses against the previous governor (Bassey & Ubi, 2012). However, an irrevocable injunction prohibiting the EFCC from looking into the state officials was given to the then-attorney general of Rivers State in March 2007.

In addition, in 2012, James Ibori, the former governor of Delta State, was found not guilty of several corruption-related charges by a Nigerian court in 2009 but was convicted to 13 years in jail by a London court after admitting guilt to ten charges, including conspiracy to launder 50 million pounds of public funds from Delta state. Ibori is accused of using public funds to buy a Mercedes car for 920,000 pounds and a 6.9 million pound property in London. This money would have been enough to improve at least some parts of Delta State, but it was taken by a corrupt leader (Ibekwe, 2014).

Another case of corruption in the region was the arrest by the EFCC of Timipre Sylva, the former Governor of Bayelsa State, for money laundering belonging to the Bayelsa state government worth \$148 million while he was in office. Also involved were former Governors of Rivers State, Peter Odili, and Akwa Ibom State, Victor Attah, as proprietors of the \$142 million Econet Company, which has yet to be refunded to their respective governments.

Similarly, between 2009 and 2017, Bayelsa got N435.9 billion, which is more than the sum received by four Northern states combined: Sokoto, Zamfara, Kebbi, and Katsina, but infrastructure development in Bayelsa is frightening. There are states in the region with no better road networks, health care facilities, and public schools; but, corruption and poor governance are a problem (Titus & Abubakar, 2020). It could be argued that pervasive corruption among political elites exacerbated the region's discontent. Corrupt leaders are channelling oil funds generated in their territory to international bank accounts. Bribes paid by international companies during Obasanjo's regime included a large sum to US Company Haliburton and its former subsidiary Kellogg Brown and Root (KBR) to secure a construction contract for a Liquefied Natural Gas Plant in Bonny Island, Rivers State, which has yet to be completed due to corrupt leaders involved in the contract (Garuba, 2009).

The political landscape in the region is dominated by corrupt, selfish, and desperate political elites willing to go to any length to gain political power. The ruling elites in the region have institutionalised corruption, so political leaders have embezzled the vast majority of the proceeds from oil sales. Despite the region being one of the top earners from the federation account, the increased allocation to 13% has not resulted in any noticeable improvement in the living conditions of the inhabitants. Indeed, under the cover of ‘constituency projects’, the legislature pays individual legislators large sums of money from their monthly allocation to spend on their constituents. These monies, on the other hand, are never accounted for, and the constituents are never informed about actual initiatives in the region.

According to Transparency International, since the 1960s, Niger Delta politicians have either stolen or wasted more than \$380 billion. For example, politicians who have lost elections could hire militants to offset their campaign losses through oil bunkering and kidnapping (Titus, 2017). One could argue that the region's significant accumulation of wealth and financial power is held by a small group of elites who abuse democracy to cause underdevelopment and encourage violent protests. Because oil is produced in the region, politicians and traditional authorities desire a larger portion of the money that comes from beneath their feet. However, because the revenues of oil make up a substantial amount of the ill-gotten riches of top public leaders in the region, Nigeria's ability to wage a meaningful anti-corruption war has been severely hampered. Indeed, after the return of democratic administration in 1999, the derivation principle has climbed to 13% in favour of oil-producing states, but state governors and NDDC officials utilise the oil funds to extend their political authority and improve their chances of corruption. The below tables and figures shows the high level of corruption based on revenue allocated from 2010 to 2018 in the region.

Table 1: Distribution of revenue allocation to state governments by federation allocation committee, 2010-2012
(Total Gross Allocation per Year)

S/No	State	Population	2010	2010 (%)	2011	2011 (%)	2012	2012 (%)
1	Abia	3,727,347	35,686,322,548.89	1.92	51,539,402,675.55	1.86	53,463,252,697.79	2.02
2	Adamawa	4,248,436	34,092,819,098.48	1.83	51,698,360,239.14	1.87	51,515,596,898.29	1.95
3	Akwa Ibom	5,482,177	187,046,527,901.63	10.1	267,370,286,739.67	9.65	254,214,588,610.13	9.61
4	Anambra	5,527,809	37,315,968,501.14	2.01	53,761,117,460.72	1.94	54,493,104,412.88	2.06
5	Bauchi	6,537,314	41,286,971,275.70	2.22	58,468,191,519.38	2.11	59,079,863,537.38	2.23
6	Bayelsa	2,277,961	99,657,106,769.73	5.36	181,352,713,599.52	6.55	158,361,431,105.99	5.98
7	Benue	5,741,815	36,303,258,787.07	1.95	52,936,281,254.87	1.91	53,333,282,719.40	2.02
8	Borno	5,860,183	43,395,156,180.74	2.33	62,375,983,786.73	2.25	61,674,987,494.83	2.33
9	Cross River	3,866,269	33,788,797,088.08	1.82	56,618,233,849.39	2.04	51,360,783,152.44	1.94
10	Delta	5,663,362	145,323,082,086.90	7.81	234,528,931,009.70	8.47	203,647,433,568.90	7.70
11	Ebonyi	2,880,383	27,816,232,419.57	1.50	37,486,817,099.41	1.35	37,861,403,448.90	1.43
12	Edo	4,235,595	39,925,535,224.76	2.15	62,939,372,206.00	2.27	58,440,420,799.10	2.21
13	Ekiti	3,270,798	31,005,819,603.97	1.67	43,498,176,656.20	1.57	39,783,693,088.91	1.50
14	Enugu	4,411,119	31,746,183,529.19	1.71	49,122,619,346.20	1.77	50,025,955,045.32	1.89
15	Gombe	3,564,126	31,472,642,702.29	1.69	45,959,862,950.39	1.66	42,173,594,773.67	1.59
16	Imo	5,408,756	39,707,788,900.04	2.13	57,757,534,131.75	2.09	57,332,110,561.81	2.17
17	Jigawa	5,828,163	39,414,963,138.93	2.12	58,160,445,124.40	2.10	58,295,790,810.42	2.20
18	Kaduna	8,252,366	44,055,192,369.96	2.37	63,726,335,091.79	2.3	64,351,640,004.72	2.43
19	Kano	13,076,892	58,854,601,761.22	3.16	83,557,862,363.21	3.02	83,388,939,712.81	3.15
20	Kastina	7,831,319	43,338,452,269.60	2.33	62,631,212,688.83	2.26	64,297,127,680.68	2.43
21	Kebbi	4,440,050	34,034,091,528.50	1.83	52,516,636,277.41	1.85	51,775,155,148.54	1.96
22	Kogi	4,473,490	35,969,657,988.46	1.93	52,114,440,468.83	1.88	52,572,277,093.64	1.99
23	Kwara	3,192,893	31,397,127,810.21	1.69	45,861,484,931.30	1.66	46,347,513,583.04	1.75
24	Lagos	12,550,598	81,703,316,412.40	4.39	115,670,786,135.39	4.18	118,592,092,475.46	4.48
25	Nasarrawa	2,528,395	30,482,783,938.84	1.64	40,824,043,993.98	1.47	41,655,390,350.10	1.57
26	Niger	5,556,247	38,441,474,992.83	2.07	56,085,949,458.84	2.02	56,832,330,483.56	2.15
27	Ogun	5,217,716	36,289,810,544.71	1.95	51,964,290,313.20	1.88	52,841,307,430.34	1.98
28	Undo	4,671,695	60,645,487,864.01	3.26	79,031,801,984.74	2.85	73,181,303,735.38	2.77
29	Osun	4,705,589	31,958,572,536.00	1.72	49,269,488,538.61	1.78	48,080,472,650.76	1.82
30	Oyo	7,840,864	41,037,461,889.58	2.21	60,481,265,622.02	2.18	62,451,236,973.07	2.36
31	Plateau	4,200,442	34,376,843,974.63	1.85	50,973,394,766.84	1.84	52,155,400,557.68	1.97
32	Rivers	7,303,924	178,556,645,721.16	9.60	271,694,346,625.25	9.81	226,525,608,940.47	8.56
33	Sokoto	4,998,090	38,340,062,936.01	2.06	54,934,620,353.26	1.98	54,804,841,696.64	2.07
34	Taraba	3,066,834	35,995,533,001.75	1.94	51,673,364,699.25	1.87	52,274,246,423.46	1.98

35	Yobe	3,294,137	35,139,298,129.09	1.89	51,196,431,721.86	1.85	51,179,452,123.24	1.93
36	Zamfara	4,515,427	34,292,708,837.71	1.84	50,266,111,028.91	1.81	48,029,298,478.22	1.81
	Total	193,392,517	1,859,894,300,263.78	100.00	2,770,048,196,712.36	100.00	2,646,392,928,267.54	100.00

Source: Data generated/ calculated by the researcher from Federal Ministry of Finance State Allocation & National Population Commission, 2016 Population Project (Available at <https://www.slideshare.net/statisense/nigeria-demography-state-by-state>).

Table 2: Distribution of revenue allocation to state governments by federation allocation committee, 2013-2015
(Total Gross Allocation per Year)

S/No	State	Population	2013	2013 (%)	2014	2014 (%)	2015	2015 (%)
1	Abia	3,727,347	61,339,825,538.23	2.10	17,260,871,352.64	2.13	40,082,563,528.57	2.27
2	Adamawa	4,248,436	58,056,157,416.48	1.98	16,168,647,027.49	2.0	37,753,050,520.67	2.13
3	Akwa Ibom	5,482,177	296,257,263,052.08	10.1	82,279,636,122.50	10.2	163,962,359,835.25	9.27
4	Anambra	5,527,809	59,157,624,764.39	2.02	16,546,357,846.47	2.04	40,962,359,835.25	2.32
5	Bauchi	6,537,314	64,779,217,067.33	2.21	18,263,583,926.67	2.25	41,209,791,034.26	2.33
6	Bayelsa	2,277,961	189,054,029,511.56	6.46	46,999,194,498.91	5.80	80,305,401,800.85	4.54
7	Benue	5,741,815	58,410,671,642.96	2.00	16,754,257,081.22	2.07	37,819,773,534.73	2.14
8	Borno	5,860,183	68,711,157,620.81	2.35	19,969,583,681.23	2.47	48,243,658,732.84	2.73
9	Cross River	3,866,269	53,665,826,497.50	1.83	15,706,012,896.90	1.94	30,036,497,990.10	1.70
10	Delta	5,663,362	219,190,363,319.34	7.49	64,264,809,490.90	7.93	120,122,741,706.71	6.79
11	Ebonyi	2,880,383	42,379,091,038.57	1.45	12,388,022,958.96	1.53	30,521,338,932.29	1.73
12	Edo	4,235,595	65,513,889,038.57	2.24	19,020,556,659.07	2.35	40,107,447,041.09	2.27
13	Ekiti	3,270,798	44,451,923,164.68	1.52	12,783,684,027.43	1.58	28,219,449,434.94	1.60
14	Enugu	4,411,119	55,466,755,615.82	1.90	16,350,045,447.07	2.02	39,034,076,131.96	2.21
15	Gombe	3,564,126	47,178,092,265.53	1.61	13,174,520,866.57	1.63	29,508,862,661.74	1.67
16	Imo	5,408,756	63,091,471,994.94	2.16	17,606,258,533.75	2.17	39,478,849,278.83	2.23
17	Jigawa	5,828,163	64,311,047,857.72	2.20	18,446,560,184.85	2.28	44,705,996,445.11	2.53
18	Kaduna	8,252,366	70,233,973,822.32	2.40	20,222,115,307.97	2.50	48,637,908,665.02	2.75
19	Kano	13,076,892	92,651,402,652.92	3.17	26,218,400,118.85	3.24	64,062,012,377.31	3.62
20	Kastina	7,831,319	69,802,508,916.39	2.39	20,041,041,582.71	2.47	48,369,024,174.45	2.73
21	Kebbi	4,440,050	58,658,498,794.16	2.00	17,179,810,532.70	2.12	40,980,037,717.45	2.32
22	Kogi	4,473,490	59,024,702,816.68	2.02	17,648,245,936.45	2.18	40,415,861,606.59	2.29
23	Kwara	3,192,893	50,252,984,054.20	1.72	14,358,600,018.24	1.77	34,051,502,675.12	1.93
24	Lagos	12,550,598	117,716,294,037.42	4.02	34,290,134,849.30	4.23	88,349,485,946.83	5.00
25	Nasarrawa	2,528,395	46,875,866,990.60	1.60	14,311,611,911.90	1.77	34,924,800,403.00	1.97
26	Niger	5,556,247	61,856,534,355.94	2.11	16,241,807,827.47	2.01	40,133,571,728.90	2.27
27	Ogun	5,217,716	57,039,047,559.95	1.95	15,515,795,880.48	1.92	34,333,291,926.57	1.94
28	Undo	4,671,695	81,594,570,389.68	2.79	21,012,056,649.78	2.59	41,614,974,587.08	2.35
29	Osun	4,705,589	46,284,237,018.57	1.58	11,107,636,850.32	1.37	20,223,138,804.75	1.14
30	Oyo	7,840,864	67,399,410,688.22	2.30	18,127,002,997.02	2.24	42,990,133,458.65	2.43
31	Plateau	4,200,442	57,074,488,053.82	1.95	17,012,768,668.54	2.10	39,062,800,358.19	2.21
32	Rivers	7,303,924	247,585,586,905.69	8.46	56,768,387,944.71	7.01	99,866,805,754.72	5.65
33	Sokoto	4,998,090	60,968,138,443.07	2.08	17,972,397,749.21	2.22	43,174,134,155.70	2.44
34	Taraba	3,066,834	56,164,956,344.56	1.92	15,572,397,066.85	1.92	36,234,305,993.24	2.05
35	Yobe	3,294,137	56,417,169,350.96	1.93	16,063,976,967.72	1.98	39,044,197,135.55	2.21
36	Zamfara	4,515,427	57,036,786,682.82	1.95	16,308,262,791.70	2.01	32,589,503,080.26	1.84
	Total	193,392,517	2,925,651,565,370.28	100	809,955,054,254.25	100	1,768,554,208,204.34	100.00

Source: Data generated/ calculated by the Researcher from Federal Ministry of Finance State Allocation & National Population Commission, 2016 Population Project (Available at <https://www.slideshare.net/statisense/nigeria-demography-state-by-state>).

Table 3: Distribution of revenue allocation to state governments by federation allocation committee, 2016-2018

S/No	State	Population	2016	2016 (%)	2017	2017 (%)	2018	2018 (%)
1	Abia	3,727,347	24,382,280,501.31	2.06	38,876,702,908.71	2.24	55,326,313,520.15	2.22
2	Adamawa	4,248,436	26,911,774,298.87	2.28	37,436,462,193.81	2.15	49,510,206,574.39	1.99
3	Akwa Ibom	5,482,177	95,446,631,800.06	8.08	143,614,945,782.83	8.26	202,365,072,519.99	8.11
4	Anambra	5,527,809	29,312,158,796.33	2.48	41,338,238,321.08	2.38	55,249,945,897.31	2.22
5	Bauchi	6,537,314	29,503,446,934.36	2.50	39,515,179,181.35	2.27	54,020,849,574.37	2.17
6	Bayelsa	2,277,961	52,731,046,387.42	4.46	105,258,243,351.38	6.05	153,104,866,273.55	6.14
7	Benue	5,741,815	29,601,578,652.97	2.51	39,801,371,551.28	2.29	55,441,078,188.72	2.22
8	Borno	5,860,183	36,691,851,175.99	3.11	46,535,736,179.14	2.68	63,271,702,953.51	2.54
9	Cross River	3,866,269	17,829,334,525.35	1.51	23,451,782,732.99	1.35	36,954,686,823.13	1.48
10	Delta	5,663,362	62,312,894,243.32	5.27	111,203,709,891.97	6.39	213,634,192,630.29	8.57
11	Ebonyi	2,880,383	24,955,457,591.79	2.11	35,490,890,739.39	2.04	44,955,009,442.29	1.8
12	Edo	4,235,595	23,298,675,678.10	1.97	36,844,999,470.25	2.12	69,169,646,683.36	2.77
13	Ekiti	3,270,798	17,130,284,022.99	1.45	25,633,665,721.07	1.47	39,325,661,893.63	1.58
14	Enugu	4,411,119	27,830,621,561.59	2.36	37,833,557,959.84	2.18	53,104,455,149.92	2.13
15	Gombe	3,564,126	19,715,274,764.06	1.67	31,232,979,502.24	1.80	43,808,127,576.80	1.76
16	Imo	5,408,756	27,770,908,410.89	2.35	38,116,470,854.23	2.19	54,181,645,137.52	2.17
17	Jigawa	5,828,163	32,651,129,597.08	2.76	45,264,749,165.01	2.60	60,327,926,310.65	2.42
18	Kaduna	8,252,366	36,047,933,715.09	3.05	50,807,097,529.88	2.92	68,849,941,237.76	2.76
19	Kano	13,076,892	46,835,313,643.01	3.96	65,140,059,241.99	3.75	84,205,898,067.21	3.38
20	Kastina	7,831,319	35,498,437,375.18	3.00	46,339,868,732.24	2.66	61,651,483,460.57	2.47
21	Kebbi	4,440,050	28,517,665,167.70	2.41	40,076,938,773.09	2.30	54,580,176,454.58	2.19
22	Kogi	4,473,490	28,653,723,345.57	2.43	39,646,840,921.91	2.28	53,376,978,657.33	2.14
23	Kwara	3,192,893	23,031,664,262.15	1.95	33,107,193,728.77	1.90	44,573,231,265.18	1.79
24	Lagos	12,550,598	72,354,419,656.52	6.12	89,694,754,919.45	5.16	119,024,027,795.54	4.77
25	Nasarrawa	2,528,395	25,689,157,643.33	2.17	35,197,763,034.99	2.02	47,550,214,527.97	1.91
26	Niger	5,556,247	28,977,846,382.49	2.45	42,473,678,019.43	2.44	57,521,609,575.96	2.31
27	Ogun	5,217,716	18,781,959,305.72	1.59	26,185,030,796.11	1.51	39,644,151,088.39	1.59
28	Undo	4,671,695	29,667,931,705.72	2.51	45,897,247,825.41	2.64	64,686,727,822.91	2.59
29	Osun	4,705,589	7,634,202,368.32	0.65	10,436,789,071.78	0.60	22,837,305,434.54	0.92
30	Oyo	7,840,864	31,171,880,876.36	2.64	44,473,339,482.89	2.56	59,289,159,988.50	2.38
31	Plateau	4,200,442	19,291,366,924.57	1.63	29,620,161,161.74	1.71	43,885,148,418.59	1.76
32	Rivers	7,303,924	67,130,857,162.68	5.68	119,632,192,162.39	6.88	172,627,019,316.69	6.92
33	Sokoto	4,998,090	30,853,258,784.87	2.61	41,243,655,071.75	2.37	54,460,056,835.47	2.18
34	Taraba	3,066,834	24,779,230,213.35	2.10	33,922,215,995.68	1.95	47,877,801,462.16	1.92
35	Yobe	3,294,137	27,662,357,213.35	2.34	39,493,537,224.69	2.27	52,874,949,262.92	2.12
36	Zamfara	4,515,427	20,750,011,537.03	1.76	28,452,828,222.31	1.64	40,831,825,094.60	1.64
Total		193,392,517	1,181,404,566,225.49	100	1,739,290,877,423.07	100	2,494,099,092,916.45	100.00

Source: Data generated/ calculated by the Researcher from Federal Ministry of Finance State Allocation & National Population Commission, 2020 Population Project (Available at <https://www.slideshare.net/statisense/nigeria-demography-state-by-state>).

However, it is evident from the above figures that comparatively, the Niger delta region takes the highest allocation among the 36 states of the federation except little or similar to that of Lagos and Kano States figures. The reason for failure of the region to experience sustainable development should not be placed on funds rather the consequence of politicisation of corruption in the region. Records have it that over ₦7trillion accrued to the states and local governments in the nine Niger Delta states in 8 years (2010 to 2018), based on the 13 per cent derivation principle, not much infrastructural development was on the ground (see Tables 1, 2 and 3 for details). It is believed that the region's most serious problem is not a lack of resources, but rather a lack of competent management or blatant recklessness in the deployment and control of those resources. For instance, Bayelsa State is one of nine states in region with large crude oil resources, according to Ibekwe (2014) the majority of Nigeria's government revenue comes from oil, which is collected and distributed by the federal government. Since Bayelsa State was established in 1996, the federal

government has given it a 13 % derivation of excess crude and statutory allocations share of oil revenues amounting to billions of dollars, but there is little to no proof that the resources are being used effectively in the state.

This is evidence on Nigeria’s income from oil over a nine-year period; Global Witness (2019) reported that Nigeria earned around US \$370 billion in oil and gas exports between 2010 and 2015. Nigeria's federal, state, and local governments divide its oil money according to a predetermined formula. This kind of revenue allocation is frequently referred to as statutory allocation. This formula's derivation idea, which returns 13% of the oil riches to the states that produce it, is one of its main tenets. Numerous local stakeholders from the oil- and non-oil-producing states routinely contest these allocations. This significant sum of money spent on gasoline hasn't made much of a dent in the region's endemic unemployment, poverty, degradation of the environment, and violent conflicts.

It could be argue that corruption is largely responsible for backwardness and developmental deficit in the region. In the past years of democratic governance in Nigeria, particularly since the implementation of 13% derivation, there has been a wide margin between the region (South- South) and other geopolitical zones in terms of revenue allocation (see Tables 1-3). Unfortunately, this has not translated to meaningful development in the region. For example, allocation to the region, which constitutes 15% of the total population of Nigeria, is greater than the total allocation that accrued to the North East, North West, and North Central Geopolitical Zones respectively (see Tables 4 and 5 and Figures 1 and 2).

Table 4: State government revenue allocation by federal allocation committee, 2010–2014 (Gross Total for Geopolitical Zones in Percentages)

S.N	Zone	Population	Population (%)	2010 (%)	2011 (%)	2012 (%)	2013 (%)	2014 (%)	2010–2014 (%)
1	North Central	25,693,282	13.51	11.13	10.79	11.45	11.59	12.16	11.42
2	North East	26,571,030	13.97	11.90	11.60	12.01	11.98	12.23	11.94
3	North West	48,942,307	25.73	15.72	15.37	16.06	16.15	16.81	16.02
4	South East	21,955,414	11.54	9.26	9.01	9.57	9.59	9.88	9.46
5	South West	38,257,260	20.11	15.20	14.44	14.92	14.14	13.91	14.52
6	South–South	28,829,288	15.15	36.79	38.79	35.99	36.54	35.13	36.65
Total		190,248,581	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Data generated/calculated by the researcher from Federal Ministry of Finance State Allocations

Table 5: Distribution of revenue allocation to state governments by federal allocation committee (Gross Total for Geopolitical Zones in Percentages), 2015–2018

S.N	Zone	Population	Population (%)	2015 (%)	2016 (%)	2017 (%)	2018 (%)	2015–2018 (%)
1	North Central	25,693,282	13.51	13.02	13.13	12.63	12.07	12.71
2	North East	26,571,030	13.97	13.15	13.99	13.12	12.49	13.19
3	North West	48,942,307	25.73	18.28	19.57	18.25	17.05	18.29
4	South East	21,955,414	11.54	10.77	11.36	11.02	10.54	10.92

5	South West	38,257,260	20.11	14.49	14.96	13.93	13.83	14.30
6	South-South	28,829,288	15.15	30.29	26.98	31.05	34.01	30.58
Total		190,248,581	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source : Data generated/ calculated by the researcher from Federal Ministry of Finance State Allocation & National Population Commission, 2016 Population Project (Available at <https://www.slideshare.net/statisense/nigeria-demography-state-by-state>)

Figure 1: Total revenue allocation to the six geopolitical zones

Source: Data generated/ calculated by the researchers from Federal Ministry of Finance State Allocation & National Population Commission, 2016 Population Project (Available at <https://www.slideshare.net/statisense/nigeria-demography-state-by-state>).

Figure 2: Six geopolitical zones' population distributions and percentages

Source: Data generated/ calculated by the researchers from Federal Ministry of Finance State Allocation & National Population Commission, 2016 Population Project (Available at <https://www.slideshare.net/statisense/nigeria-demography-state-by-state>)

According to a thorough review of revenue distribution from 2010 to 2018, the 13% allocation to states with an oil companies actually made up 34% of the total federal allocation to states in the federation (see Figure 1). The NDDC, which has a ₦503.5 billion budget from 2010 to 2018, as well as other development organisations' budgets, are not included in this. The argument here is that political, bureaucratic, and institutional corruption have harmed the region's growth prospects. The region's massive allocation had been blatantly plundered by the same persons in the region. The huge budget for the region has not resulted in better basic facilities or a higher standard of living. The majority of the cash allocated are embezzled or misapplied. This act of corruption has thrown the state into disarray, with residents fighting and demanding for a better quality of life.

Corruption has aided in the improvement of the region's ineffective bureaucracy (weak institutions). Two instances of bureaucratic processes that frequently take longer than anticipated include getting different types of approvals and getting construction sites approved. Bureaucrats' purposeful attempts to increase their official pay are the cause of the delay. This paper argues that improving people's lives in the region necessitates eradicating corruption at all levels of

government, including municipal and state administrations. This is because corruption not only causes underdevelopment in the region, but it also encourages insurrection because the region's elites promote it.

Conclusion and recommendations

Scholars' perspectives on the region's issues are typically divergent. However, there appears to be a widespread belief that the region's most serious problem is a development crisis. The problem, according to this study, is actually quite complex, spanning from the area's geology and topography to the Nigerian state's flawed federalism and other concerns of neglect from oil firms operating in the area. To this end, it was stated that a holistic understanding of the region's situation necessitates a critical examination of issues of politicisation of corruption, which affect all of the region's developmental policies and programmes. Thus, given the detrimental effects of corruption in the region this paper recommended the following steps to nip in the bud such menace. First, drastic and critical steps must be taken by the current regime of President Buhari through anti-corruption agencies to curb all forms of corrupt practices in the region. Second, Federal Government should be publishing all revenue allocations to States and Local Government level using grassroots method in order to create awareness how the funds are been used. This would further expose the heinous act in the region when all the stakeholders have idea of the financial status. Third, there should be stiffer penalty of life imprisonment with no option for fine, depending on the magnitude of the stealing. From 1billion naira live imprison, less than 1billion naira 50 years. This would be deterring people from stealing public funds and it would ensure development in the region. Forth, any strategy needed to address the development deficits currently affecting the region must include a review of the factors that encourage corruption in the region and the strengthening of the systems that could help in the management of all types of conflicts in the region, which is the root cause of corruption.

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